

Effects of Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) on Optical Properties of Waste Paper

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Abstract:

Waste paper is used in pulp and paper production as secondary raw material. It consists of clean rejects/trimmings from paper mills, but may also comprise household waste and waste from a very wide range of economic sectors. Waste paper comes from printing works, paper processing plants, department stores, self-service stores and homes. The aim of this study was to improve optical properties of waste paper which has low brightness. To this end, 3 different kinds of waste papers were used in this study. Printing paper, newspaper and packaging paper were recycled and produced handsheets with using Precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) as filler. Ground calcium carbonate (GCC) was also used for comparing with PCC. According to obtained results, optical properties of waste papers were improved by using PCC and GCC. On the other hand, Papers produced with using PCC were higher optical properties than GCC's. Although there were decreases on physical properties of papers, physical properties of waste paper obtained with using PCC were better than GCC's.

Keywords: Wastepaper; Precipitated, Ground, Calcium, Carbonate

Introduction:

Addition of mineral substances has been practiced since early years of production of paper. Due to increasing paper types, using filler in some paper production has become inevitable. Today, mainly of calcium carbonate, kaolin, talc, titanium dioxide and calcium sulphate are widely used in paper industry (Eroğlu, 1990 ; Tutuş ve Karademir, 2003).

Fillers used in the paper industry are basically two main reasons. These are making production system more economical and changes technical specifications of paper (Karademir et al., 2003). Shape, average particle size, size distribution, specific surface area and total size are important parameters in determining properties of paper (Han and Seo, 1997).

In paper production, fillers are generally used in improving optical properties of paper as opacity, brightness. Also, fillers improve paper formation, surface smoothness, ink absorption and reduce cost due to difference in price between fiber and filler. Due to fillers used in paper production is decreasing number of fiber-fiber bond. Therefore, reductions in paper strength properties are occurred. For

this reason, paper-makers must determine rate of filler considering strength properties (Haller et al. 2001).

Waste paper is used in pulp and paper production as secondary raw material. There are two main categories of waste papers, pre-consumer waste, and post-consumer waste. Pre-consumer waste is material which left the paper mill but was discarded before it was ready for consumer use. Post-consumer waste is material discarded after consumer use.

The objective of the study was to improve optical properties of waste paper and to investigate effects of Precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and Ground calcium carbonate (GCC). For this reason, 3 different kinds of waste papers are recycled and produced handsheets with using PCC and GCC as filler. To this end, optical and physical properties of waste papers were determined.

Materials and Methods:

Printing paper, newspaper and packaging paper were recycled and used in this study. PCC which has scalenohedral morphology 2.5 µm and GCC are taken from Adaçal Ind. Min.

Printing paper, newspaper and packaging paper are collected and disintegrated into fibers. At the end of recycling, pulp was pressed up to 20-25% dryness. Later on, moisture content of pulps regulated to 20-25% and placed in polyethylene bags and moisture content was determined. PCC and GCC were added specific ratios for each waste papers shown Table 1. Handsheets of recycled waste papers with grammages of 70 g/m² were prepared according to Tappi T 272 om-92 and made on a Rapid Kothen machine.

Table 1. PCC and GCC ratios used in paper production

	PCC Ratio (%)	GCC Ratio (%)
1	0	0
2	20	0
3	25	0
4	30	0
5	0	20
6	0	25
7	0	30

Physical and optical properties of handsheets were measured according to Tappi Standart Test Methods given below.

Table 2. Optical properties of printing paper used PCC and GCC

Optical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Whiteness	74.76	78.94	80.30	81.38	77.93	78.01	78.38
Brightness	79.71	83.03	84.01	85.19	82.12	81.78	82.15
Yellowness	-7.36	-5.81	-5.20	-5.37	-5.94	-5.29	-5.30
Opacity	96.81	97.98	97.68	98.58	97.70	97.64	97.66

In Table 3, results show that newspapers used PCC have higher optical properties than GCC. It is observed that whiteness and brightness of

Table 3. Optical properties of newspaper used PCC and GCC

Optical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Whiteness	48.30	56.85	59.38	62.29	56.01	56.59	59.05
Brightness	45.56	54.37	57.15	60.23	52.72	54.04	56.56
Yellowness	7.55	6.04	5.13	4.57	6.81	6.31	5.92
Opacity	79.69	99.80	99.87	99.90	99.60	99.78	99.86

In Table 4, obtained results show that packaging papers used PCC have higher optical properties than GCC. It is observed that whiteness and brightness of newspapers used

Table 4. Optical properties of packaging paper used PCC and GCC

Optical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Whiteness	29,99	34,26	36,35	42,76	35,56	39,34	40,90
Brightness	19,46	23,08	25,04	31,85	24,44	27,92	29,26
Yellowness	53,34	49,41	46,87	38,34	46,87	43,41	42,44
Opacity	99,68	99,46	99,58	99,59	99,63	99,00	99,45

- Breaking Length: H.E Messmer, Testometric 220M (Anonymous, 1992)
- Tear Index: Elmendorf Tearing Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Burst Index: B.F. Perkins & Son, Mullen Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Brightness, Whiteness, Yellowness and Opacity: Datacolor Elrepho (Anonymous, 1997)

Results and Discussion:

Optical properties of waste papers obtained from printing paper, newspaper and packaging paper are given in Table 2, 3 and 4.

In Table 2, when comparing PCC with GCC, it is observed that optical properties of printing papers used PCC are higher than GCC. Also, whiteness and brightness of printing papers used PCC (%30) are increased %8.85 and 6.87, respectively and yellowness is decreased %19.29 compared with control samples.

newspapers used PCC are increased %28.96 and %32.19, respectively and yellowness is decreased %39.47.

PCC are increased %42.58 and %63.67, respectively and yellowness is decreased %28.12.

In a study, it is determined that PCC has higher whiteness and brightness than GCC (Müdüroğlu and Arsoy, 2012). In another study, it is determined that PCC has an increase on the optical properties of papers (Tutuş et al. 2012).

5, the results show that packaging papers used PCC have higher physical properties than GCC. Breaking length, burst index and tear index of packaging papers used PCC (%25) are higher than GCC (%25) about %14.69, %8.82 and %10.71, respectively.

Physical properties of waste papers used PCC and GCC are given in Table 5, 6 and 7. In Table

Table 5. Physical properties of packaging paper used PCC and GCC

Physical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Breaking Length (m)	2652	1850	1452	749	1502	1266	969
Burst Index	1.59	1.07	0.74	0.41	1.02	0.68	0.51
Tear Index	1.57	1.36	1.24	0.83	1.36	1.12	0.84

According to results in Table 6, breaking length, burst index and tear index of newspapers used

PCC (%20) are higher than GCC (%20) about %52.17, %47.36 and %32.98, respectively.

Table 6. Physical properties of newspaper used PCC and GCC

Physical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Breaking Length (m)	3305	2027	1744	1366	1332	1738	1558
Burst Index	2.17	1.12	0.90	0.77	0.76	1.06	0.90
Tear Index	1.36	1.25	0.95	0.84	0.94	0.84	0.84

Physical properties of printing papers used PCC and GCC are given Table 7. The obtained

results show that printing papers used GCC have higher physical properties than PCC:

Table 7. Physical properties of printing papers used PCC and GCC

Physical Properties	Control	PCC Ratio (%)			GCC Ratio (%)		
		20	25	30	20	25	30
Breaking Length (m)	2622	1544	1246	1016	2079	1740	1695
Burst Index	1.67	0.82	0.50	0.42	1.14	0.88	0.89
Tear Index	1.05	0.62	0.63	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.73

Tutus et al. 2012 found that using PCC improves physical properties when compared with other fillers. In another study, papers used PCC have higher physical properties than other fillers (Koivunen and Paulapuro, 2010)

greater brightness and opacity on paper. Because PCC has an excellent light scattering ability and inner whiteness, brightness, and chemical purity.

The results show that optical properties of waste papers used PCC were higher than GCC. Also, it was found that physical properties of waste papers used PCC were better than GCC. According to results PCC offers the following advantages;

- Using PCC during the paper production there are improves in retention because of increased bonds between fibers when compared with other fillers.
- PCC reduces costs by increasing amount of filler in paper.
- PCC allows machine to run more regularly by stabilizing water drainage.
- PCC decreases dusts during paper production.

- Using PCC on paper production, in comparison with all other fillers, provides a

6. PCC with scalenohedral morphology improves bulkiness and surface smoothness.
7. Balancing ink absorption PCC increases print quality.
8. Physical properties of papers using PCC are higher than other fillers due to better PCC grip between fibers.

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